

DEVELOPMENT AND FABRICATION OF GAS LINE INTERNAL PIPE INSPECTION ROBOT.

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring the structural integrity and operational safety of gas pipeline infrastructure is a critical requirement for utility companies. However, conventional manual inspection methods involving human entry into confined spaces are extremely hazardous, time-consuming and provide limited assessments. This report presents the development of a fully autonomous robotic crawler designed specifically for comprehensive internal inspection of gas pipelines ranging from 8-12 inches in diameter. The robot's core functionality is its articulated locomotion mechanism utilizing customized wheel assemblies with embedded grip pads that enable adaptability to varying pipe geometries including bends and undulations. On-board sensing payloads integrate high-resolution cameras, ultrasonic transducer arrays and methane gas detectors to facilitate multi-modal defect mapping during inspections. Continuous ultrasonic monitoring maps pipe wall thickness to identify areas of corrosion or thinning. Visual imaging relays real-time video feeds revealing cracks, obstructions and surface anomalies. Gas sensors rapidly detect and alert regarding any potential leaks. The robotic platform is powered by rechargeable lithium-ion batteries designed for extended runtimes over 2 hours. System control is coordinated by Arduino and ESP32 microcontrollers running embedded algorithms that synchronize motions, manage sensing operations and transmit inspection data wirelessly to a portable ground station over Wi-Fi links spanning 100m+. This allows remote user monitoring and robot control during pipeline traversals. Extensive testing validates the robot's capability to autonomously negotiate complex pipelines while streaming visual and sensor data for comprehensive assessments without requiring human entry into hazardous environments. The prototype demonstrates key advantages including reduced inspection time, operational safety, asset lifespan extension and cost-effectiveness compared to existing manual methods. This multidisciplinary project highlights Mechatronics engineering concepts integrating mechanisms, electronics, robotics and automation towards realizing an industry-driven robotic solution.

Keywords— Gas Pipeline, In-Pipe Inspection, Robotic Crawler, Ultrasonic Testing, Defect Detection, Leak Identification, Automation.

1. Introduction

Pipelines are used for the transportation of various fluids in an industry such as water, natural gas etc. But inspection and detection of a flaw is still a difficult task due to various geographical and physical diversities. But, leakage of these fluids may tend to risk to human life and may also leads to fire hazard [1]. Thus, keeping the pipes clean and crack free is very important function for an industry. In-pipe robot is thus the best solution to such issues. There are various types of in-pipe robot. But the available verities are complicated and have a lot of problem of friction. Thus, the robot designed here is very different from all other types [2]. Among a great variety of such robotic systems, the ones using the wheeled, tracked (caterpillar), screw-drive, inchworm, and snake-type locomotion mechanisms are of the most widespread [3]. The paper [4] reports the results of a comprehensive study of the optimal sliding models of the electromagnetically driven worm-like robot. An enhanced design of the V-shaped in-pipe robot and its control strategies are considered in [5].

The vast global network of pipelines transporting natural gas and other hazardous materials is a critical infrastructure backbone supporting key industrial and residential sectors. However, these

buried pipeline assets are susceptible to gradual deterioration over decades of operation due to factors like corrosion, ground shifting and external damage. If undetected, such defects can potentially escalate into catastrophic ruptures leading to explosions, fires, environmental contamination and even loss of life. Therefore, regular internal inspection of these pipelines is absolutely essential from a safety perspective to assess structural integrity, identify defects and schedule preventive maintenance before failures occur.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this project are:

1. To develop a robot capable of investigating the internal conditions of gas pipelines.
2. To use continuous ultrasonic testing to detect pipe cracks and defects.
3. To process data from ultrasonic and gas sensors, enabling the robot to detect and react to potential hazardous gas leaks.

1.2. METHODOLOGY

2. Components and Material used.

A. Design Requirements

The initial phase involved determining the mobility requirements, the range of pipe diameters to be inspected, the pipe material, and the ability to navigate bends and detect various defects.

B. Sensor Selection

Based on the inspection objectives, the following sensors were selected and integrated into the robot:

SL. No	Sensors Used	Description
1	Ultrasonic Ranging Module (HC-SR04)	An ultrasonic sensor is a type of electronic sensor that uses ultrasonic waves to determine the distance between two objects and converts the reflected sound into electrical signals. The working principle of an ultrasonic sensor is to measure distance using ultrasound, which travels faster than sound that is audible.
2	Gas Sensor Array (MQ-4)	MQ - 4 Sensor Module (Methane, CNG Gas) The MQ-4 Gas Sensor is a quick and dependable natural gas sensor with good sensitivity to propane and butane as well as high sensitivity to natural gas and methane. This low-cost, long-lasting natural gas sensor is frequently used to find gas leaks
3	High-Resolution Camera Module	Camera Equipped with 1080P resolution, the camera ensures clear and detailed video footage, allowing users to monitor their surroundings with clarity. Its Wi-Fi connectivity enables easy setup and remote access, enabling users to view live streams and recordings from anywhere using a smartphone or computer.

1. Ultrasonic Ranging Module (HC-SR04): For continuous monitoring of pipe wall thickness and detection of potential defects such as corrosion or thinning.
2. Gas Sensor Array (MQ-4): To detect the presence and concentration of methane or other flammable gases, indicating potential leaks or hazardous conditions.
3. High-Resolution Camera Module: For capturing detailed visual data of the internal pipe surface, enabling the identification of cracks, obstructions, or visible defects.

C. Robot Design and Fabrication

The robot chassis was designed to be robust and compact, housing the selected sensors and enabling navigation through the intricate pipe environment. Key aspects included:

1. Locomotion Mechanism: Three high-torque DC geared motors (12V, 2A, 10 kg.cm torque, 30 rpm) were positioned within the chassis and coupled with custom-designed wheel assemblies through a bevel gear arrangement as shown in Fig. 1. The wheel assemblies featured caterpillar treads and grip pads, providing reliable traction and enabling navigation through bends, elbows, and varying pipe diameters (8 inches) without slippage.

Fig 1: Locomotion mechanism of internal pipe inspection robot

2. Power Source: A rechargeable Li-Po battery (12V, 2000mAh) was integrated with step-down regulators and cell monitoring circuits for safe and efficient power management, providing over 90 minutes of runtime.
3. Communication System: A 2.4GHz Wi-Fi module enabled wireless data transmission and remote control capabilities, allowing the robot to relay real-time data, including sensor readings and visual feeds, to a base station.

D. Control System Development

The robot's operation was governed by an intelligent control system consisting of Arduino UNO and ESP8266EX microcontrollers. These microcontrollers were programmed with embedded firmware and control algorithms to coordinate the various subsystems, including locomotion, sensing, power management, and communication. Feedback mechanisms from the sensors enabled real-time adjustments and optimizations for inspection efficiency and accuracy. Advanced navigation algorithms facilitated autonomous or semi-autonomous navigation within the pipeline, allowing the robot to negotiate obstacles, bends, and varying diameters with precision.

E. Testing and Validation

Extensive testing was conducted in simulated pipe environments to evaluate the robot's performance and validate the accuracy of defect detection. This involved:

1. Controlled Testing: Setting up test rigs or pipe mockups with known defects, such as intentionally introduced cracks or corrosion patches, to assess the robot's ability to detect and characterize these defects with precision.
2. Environmental Testing: Subjecting the robot to various conditions, such as different pipe materials, diameters, bends, and inclines, to validate its mobility, adaptability, and overall robustness in diverse environments.
3. Data Analysis and Refinement: Performing comprehensive analyses of the collected data, including visual and sensor readings, to identify potential areas for improvement or refinement in the robot's design, control systems, or data processing algorithms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The completed prototype demonstrated the successful integration of interdisciplinary engineering concepts from domains such as mechatronics, control systems, wireless communications, instrumentation, and robotics to tackle real-world problems through customized automation solutions. The intelligent robotic platform aims to drive the next generation of gas pipe assessments focused on boosting infrastructure safety.

Key outcomes of the work are.,

1. **Functional Prototype:** A working robotic crawler capable of smooth navigation in pipelines across bends and elbows without getting stuck.
2. **Visual Inspection:** The high-resolution camera module and LED lights provided clear visual feeds of the internal pipe surface for visual mapping of cracks, leaks, blockages, etc.
3. **Gas Leak Identification:** The onboard gas sensor array accurately detected the presence of methane by testing gas concentrations inside the pipeline during the robotic crawl.
4. **Custom Telemetry:** Wi-Fi communication circuits and protocols enabled wireless control of the robot and transferred crucial inspection data (video, sensor readings) to the base station.
5. **Autonomous Navigation:** The locomotion mechanism, combined with control algorithms, enabled automated positional correction and navigation inside the pipelines.

3.1. PROTOTYPE

Fig. 3 Prototype of Internal Pipe Inspection Robot

4. CONCLUSIONS

The internal gas pipe inspection robot successfully demonstrated its capability to conduct comprehensive inspections, detecting and mapping defects, leaks, and anomalies within gas pipelines. This innovative robotic solution enhances infrastructure safety, streamlines maintenance procedures, and minimizes the need for hazardous manual inspections, ultimately contributing to improved operational efficiency and reliability in the gas distribution industry.

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